

Deliverable D7.8

Evaluation report for Communications with policymakers (1 | 2)

Deliverable report

Deliverable No.	D7.8	Work Package No.	WP7	Task/s No.	Tasks 7.4
Work Package Title	MECHANISMS FOR SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE & INTERACTION WITH THE POLICYMAKERS				
Linked Task/s Title	T7.4 Requirements for Communication with policymakers & public bodies.				
Status	Final	(Draft/Draft Final/Final)			
Dissemination level	PU	(PU-Public, PP, RE-Restricted, CO-Confidential)			
Due date deliverable	2024-05-31	Submission date	2024-05-31		
Deliverable version	2.0				

Document Contributors

Deliverable responsible	ANEFA	
Contributors	Organisation	
César Luaces Frades	ANEFA	
Lorena Viladés Santos	ANEFA	
Reviewers	Organisation	
Philipp Hartlieb	MUL	
Serdar Sadik	APP	
Paulo Romero	ANEFA	
Eduardo García	Zabala	
Violeta Vazquez	Zabala	

Document History

Version	Date	Comment
1.0	2024-05-27	First version
2.0	2024-05-29	Final version

Disclaimer

This document reflects only the authors' view. Responsibility for the information and views expressed therein lies entirely with the authors. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as consequence of project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policy makers) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analysing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analysed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allows a close follow up of main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them along the whole project activities. Among potential social risks, impact in the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

Table of Contents

Deliverable report	2
Document Contributors.....	2
Document History	2
Disclaimer	3
Table of Contents	4
List of Abbreviations	5
1 Executive Summary	6
2 General Approach	7
2.1 Plan for the close interaction between DIGIECOQUARRY and the policymakers and public bodies.	8
2.1.1 Participation in enquiries and surveys	8
2.1.2 Meetings and policy briefings	8
2.1.3 Invitation to policymakers and public bodies	9
2.1.4 The role of ANEFA	9
3 Policy Engagement Activities	10
4 Neutral Aggregates 2050	16
5 KPIs.....	17
5.1 Evidence.....	17
5.2 KPIs.....	18
6 Conclusions	19
7 References	20
List of Figures	21
Annex 1	22
Annex 2. Policymakers list.....	33

List of Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	DESCRIPTION
D	Deliverable
DEQ	DIGIECOQUARRY
IQS	Intelligent Quarrying System
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PM	Policy maker
PC	Project Coordinator
CM	Consortium Members
WP	Work Package
WP Leader	Work Package Leader
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisation
IAB	International Advisory Board
RMIS	Raw Materials Information System

1 Executive Summary

This document compiles and evaluates the DIGIECOQUARRY's dissemination actions that have been carried out to reach policymakers during these 36 months.

This deliverable is directly related to *D7.6 Requirements for communication with policymakers and public bodies* and *D7.7 Communications with policymakers' plan* as it analyses and assesses the results of the strategies and plans set by them.

D7.8 has been developed under *WP7 Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policymakers*, aiming to define and implement one-way and two-way interactions with policymakers, more specifically within task *7.4 Requirements for communication with policymakers & public bodies*, led by ANEFA and the partners involved are Montanuniversität Leoben, Chalmers University, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM-AI), Dirección General de Asturias, Fundación Asturiana de la Energía, Asogravas, Mintek, and Zabala.

The conclusions of this deliverable will be further updated by the end of the project in *D7.9 Evaluation report for communications with policymakers (2|2)*.

2 General Approach

The main objective of the interaction with policymakers is to achieve external engagement, seek international cooperation, share knowledge and best practices and improve the general perception of the quarrying industry.

The relationship between DIGIECOQUARRY's objectives and those of the communication with policymakers and public bodies are stated in *D7.6 Requirements for Communication with policymakers and public bodies—section 3*.

DEQ has 25 partners, with several linked third parties, from 10 countries (2 of them non-EU), which means that there are a vast number of policymakers, regulators and public bodies of interest for the project at national, regional and local levels, in addition to European and international bodies. Therefore, it is easy to understand the complexity of managing, implementing, recording, monitoring and evaluating such communication.

This is further complicated by the fact that the project and its communication materials are conducted in English, whereas in national, regional, and local interactions, the local language is, the language of reference.

Nevertheless, a simplified plan as possible was prepared in *D7.7 Communications with policymakers' plan*. On the one hand, it ensures the fulfilment of the objectives and serves as a reference for all CM. On the other hand, it avoids falling into unproductive bureaucracy that diverts the participants' resources away from the project's objectives.

As pragmatically as possible, three main types of communication actions have been distinguished, which are further developed in the above-mentioned document.

- Periodic and recurrent communication.
- Specific communication according to the needs of the project.
- Interaction between DEQ and the policymakers and public bodies.

For the successful implementation of the Plan, it has been essential that each member of the consortium:

a) **Identified** those policymakers, regulators and public bodies at national, regional, and local levels who are relevant to the project. These should include members of parliament and other legislative and representative bodies, members of public administrations and governments, academia and research actors, technology centres, standardisation bodies, business organisations, aggregates companies, technology developers and suppliers, machinery suppliers, construction sector associations and other aggregates industry clients, citizens and civil society in general, citizens and civil society close to aggregates sites, trade unions, NGOs and environmental networks, thinktanks, other lobbying entities, and journalists from mainstream media.

b) **Created a database** with the above-mentioned policymakers, available in Annex 2. Policymakers list

c) Used **adequate communication materials**, based on those produced during the development of the project as described in *D9.1 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan*, *D9.2 DIGIECOQUARRY's website*, and *D9.3 and D9.5 and D9.8 Dissemination and Communication materials*. These include leaflets, brochures, posters, and written texts such as press releases, articles or scientific publications.

The difference between communicating the project to policymakers, as opposed to a general audience, is that only the relevant information, based on the nature of the policymakers, is selected. The objective is to send little and addressed information to arouse the interest and attention of the listeners instead of saturating the communication channel and making the action unproductive.

The need for communication may arise due to project evolution and could be related to one or more reasons, e.g. new regulations and standards applicable to mining, expert insights, or improved collaboration. In the event of any of these, the Consortium Member involved will bring it to the attention of the relevant Task Leader and WP Leader.

In the framework of the WP concerned, the matter will be shaped and reported to the ANEFA coordination team, which will collaborate to study the case and identify the policymaker(s) involved. These may be international, EU, national,

regional or local. This internal approach will be the same whether the matter is of a positive nature, such as a proactive effort to keep policymakers informed or lobby for new standards or legislation, or if it is an issue that needs resolution.

Once the issue is appropriately formulated (as a consultation, proposal, request, contribution, report, etc.) it will be sent by ANEFA as project coordinator on behalf of the Consortium to the relevant policymaker(s). If necessary, it would be accompanied by a meeting request.

ANEFA will be the one making the follow-up. If the communication is at a national, regional, or local level, the collaboration of the WP Leaders and a CM of this country will be requested.

2.1 Plan for the close interaction between DIGIECOQUARRY and the policymakers and public bodies.

It is key for the success of DEQ to interact with policymakers and public bodies through enquiries and surveys, policy briefings, meetings, and participation in events and conferences.

2.1.1 Participation in enquiries and surveys

When, in a Task, an enquiry or a survey for policymakers and public bodies is foreseen or needed, the Task Leader will inform both the WP Leader and ANEFA as coordinator. They will evaluate if the collaboration of other partners is required and, if this is the case, they will be invited to join.

The following points must be agreed together:

- Enquiry or survey final content.
- Reply methodology and format: online, written, during a meeting, in a focus group, etc.
- Spokesperson.
- Launch date and calendar.
- Follow-up responsible(s).
- Other.

After the end of the enquiry or the survey, the responsible partner will deliver to ANEFA a short report on the participation of the policymakers and public bodies.

2.1.2 Meetings and policy briefings

When, in a Task, a meeting or a policy briefing with policymakers (Administrations, political parties, relevant related organisations like entrepreneur organisations, Trade Unions, Accademia, Technological Centres, NGOs, etc.) and public bodies, at EU, national, regional, local and international levels, is foreseen or needed to explain DEQ and to discuss potential issues and difficulties identified that could require political actions (policy, legislation, or other) the CM will directly proceed.

The meetings will be organised, as appropriate, in face-to-face, online or hybrid modes, or even with visits to some of the pilot sites.

If a project team member needs support or information, they are encouraged to ask the Task Leader, WP Leader, or ANEFA as the coordinator. ANEFA and the leaders of WP7 and WP8 (Zabala and UPM-AI) will work together closely to coordinate messages and ensure a cohesive proposal.

If any marketing material is needed, ANEFA shall be contacted to provide it.

Whenever a relevant meeting or policy briefing to the project takes place, after giving feedback to the Task Leader or WP Leader, ANEFA must always be notified as coordinator. Besides, if there are records (programme, agenda, minutes, signature list, pictures, video, etc.), the Consortium Member participating will send the available information to ANEFA.

2.1.3 Invitation to policymakers and public bodies

In the work programme of DEQ, several workshops, seminars, panel presentations and a final conference are scheduled and are being celebrated. During the four-year lifespan of the project, it is foreseen to participate and organise scientific conferences, events, trade fairs, exhibitions, business events, information days, technical committees, assemblies, etc.

Selected and appropriate policymakers and public bodies have been and will be invited to these events:

- DIGIECOQUARRY's workshops, seminars and panel presentations.
- DIGIECOQUARRY 's final conference.
- Scientific conferences.
- Other events, trade fairs and workshops (exhibitions, business events, information days, technical committees, assemblies, etc.).

2.1.4 The role of ANEFA

ANEFA, as the Spanish Aggregates Association, is the leading voice for the extractive sector in Spain. It plays a crucial role in various aspects of the extractive industry, positioning itself as a key player in both national and European contexts. ANEFA is actively involved in strategic planning, legislative advocacy, and policy development to ensure effective representation of the sector's interests.

In response to climate change and energy transition policies, ANEFA is proactive, submitting numerous responses to legislative initiatives and participating in the development of key regulations. This includes drafting the Climate Neutrality Roadmap for Aggregates and contributing to guidelines for water management and end-of-waste criteria.

ANEFA is also instrumental in advocating for occupational health and safety measures, particularly regarding respirable crystalline silica. It implements action plans, develops technical guidelines, and campaigns against proposals that could negatively impact the industry's safety standards.

Moreover, ANEFA is committed to research, innovation, and training, ensuring the sector remains competitive and sustainable. Through various projects and initiatives, it facilitates knowledge exchange, skill development, and technological advancements within the industry.

3 Policy Engagement Activities

As mentioned before, engaging with policymakers can be done through various methods. Meetings provide opportunities for discussions, decision-making, and relationship-building. Participating in fairs and congresses can provide valuable networking opportunities and insights into industry trends, while webinars are convenient online tools that can deliver information and engage stakeholders.

ANEFA, as the leading partner for the interaction with policymakers, has conducted a wide range of activities to reach as many of them as possible. Other partners, like Asogravas, Chalmers University and UPM-AI have also contributed to this task. A total of 192 actions, carried out in different countries and the different ways mentioned above, have been registered in the breakdown of which is given below.

Figure 1 Type of action – Number.

Meetings, in which DEQ is explained, dominate at 87.98%, underscoring the significance of direct interactions and the importance of face-to-face discussions in shaping policies. Fairs and congresses represent 6% of the actions, indicating a presence in public forums for policy dissemination and engagement. Workshops contribute 4% and webinars 1%, showcasing the use of training events for policy discussions.

Figure 2 Type of action - %.

Figure 3. DEQ workshop's opening, Spain.

Figure 4. DEQ at PDAC 2023 fair, Canada.

Figure 5. DEQ at Hannover Messe fair, Germany.

Figure 6. DEQ at ANEFA's General Assembly 2023, Spain.

Figure 7. DEQ at GAIN Summit, Korea.

Figure 8. DEQ at Mining and Energy International Congress, Spain.

Further details of these meetings can be read in D9.4, D9.6, and D9.9. Report on Dissemination and Communication activities (1,2 & 3/4).

Conveying information from DEQ at events has been accomplished through presentations, written notes, verbal communication, and more. The flexible use of these various communication channels demonstrates a strategic and adaptable approach, accommodating different communication preferences and situations.

Figure 9 Information conveyed through- Number of times.

Talking about DIGIECOQUARRY encompassed in another presentation takes the lead with 39%, showcasing its adaptability to effectively meet policymakers’ needs. Following closely is giving verbal information at 33%, facilitating real-time interaction and query clarification. Making a complete specific presentation offers a thorough exploration, accounting for 11% of engagement. Other means such as adding notes in reports, liaison meetings, roundtables, workshops, showcasing roll-ups, setting up stands, or through the Neutral aggregates 2050 roadmap have been used.

Figure 10 Dissemination channel used - %.

It is estimated that DEQ has reached at least 7140 policymakers. Depending on their nature, they have been divided into the following groups:

- Academia and researchers
- Certification bodies
- Citizens and civil society
- Communication media
- Construction sector and other clients. Construction Products Confederations
- Construction sector and other clients. Others
- Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
- Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
- Environmental NGOs
- ICT & suppliers' industries
- Official policymakers and funding bodies
- Public interest Foundations

Systematically recording the participation of each group in 192 activities has produced the following compiled results:

Figure 11 Actions with incidence into policy makers (by category).

Aggregates Associations demonstrate really high involvement, being present in 91.67% of the activities. Official policymakers and funding bodies (60.94%) closely follow, indicating their pivotal roles in shaping policies. Academia and researchers (52%) also hold a notable position in engagement. The remaining categories also exhibit considerable engagement levels: Environmental NGOs, Citizens and civil society, the Construction sector and other clients, M&Q Associations, Communication media, and Certification bodies, ranging from 25% to 34%. ICT and suppliers' industries, as well as public interest foundations, show relatively lower engagement at 13% and 12%, which highlights the importance of collaborative efforts across sectors to positively influence policy decisions.

Figure 12 Percentage of actions reaching types of policymakers (by category).

In addition to the politicians engaged at the previously named events, a contact list has been compiled as mentioned in *General Approach* section (Annex 2. Policymakers list) comprising 523 individuals who receive periodic communications about the project. The origin of these individuals is as follows:

Figure 13 Types of policymakers - %.

4 Neutral Aggregates 2050

To date, the most remarkable outcome of the interaction with policymakers has been the launch of the Roadmap for Climate Neutrality in the Aggregates Industry - Neutral Aggregates 2050.

The Roadmap addresses critical topics for the sector, including European policies, the aggregates production process, and its role in achieving climate neutrality. It outlines the sector's requirements regarding public policies and identifies key performance indicators relevant to this domain. The roadmap serves a dual purpose: internally, to drive industry implementation, and externally, to communicate to stakeholders how the sector operates and its contributions to climate change mitigation objectives.

DEQ played a pivotal role in conceptualising, writing, reviewing, and editing, as well as translating into different languages, this roadmap through its involvement with Aggregates Europe-UEPG, which coordinated the efforts of over 10 countries in its formulation.

Figure 14 Neutral Aggregates cover.

It can be read here: https://www.aggregates-europe.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/UEPG-Roadmap-on-Climate-Change-2023-1_compressed.pdf

5 KPIs

To support and monitor interactions with policymakers and public bodies, data have been gathered to calculate the KPIs as stated in D7.7.

5.1 Evidence

When engaging with policymakers and public bodies, presenting physical verifiable evidence for all activities may not always be feasible. However, for DEQ, the following objective evidence will be taken into consideration:

E.1] Contacts list used for the distribution of:

- **Promotional material** (brochures leaflets, posters, or infographics).
- **Publications** (press releases, online newsletter, dissemination and communication articles in journals and magazines, scientific publications, public deliverables, joint public-private publications, letters, specific reports, or executive summaries).
- **Invitations** to public events.

E.2] **Emails and letters** asking for meetings or inviting policymakers and public bodies to events or accompanying communication materials, when existing.

E.3] **Agendas or programs** of the meetings with policymakers and public bodies when existing.

E.4] **Pictures or videos** of the meetings with policymakers and public bodies when existing.

E.5] **Minutes or written reports** of the meetings with policymakers and public bodies when existing.

E.6] **Attendance/signature** of the meetings with policymakers and public bodies when existing.

E.7] **Surveys or reports** completed by policymakers and public bodies when applicable.

E.8] **Verbal report** of the meeting or the communication action.

E.9] **Communication materials** produced for interactions with policymakers.

E.10] **Evaluable results** and outcomes from interactions with policymakers.

5.2 KPIs

For assessing the communication impact of policymakers and public bodies, the following simple Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are suggested.

Table 1 KPI table.

KPI	Description	Evidence	Result
A	Number of policymakers and public bodies identified, listed, and included in the database.	E1	523
B	Number of policymakers and public bodies invited to meetings (individual or collective).	E1, E2	13891
C	Number of meetings (individual or collective) with policymakers and public bodies.	E3, E4, E5, E6, E8	167
D	Number of policymakers and public bodies contacted in meetings (individual or collective).	E3, E4, E5, E6, E8	7139
E	Number of different policymakers and public bodies contacted with communication materials.	E1, E2, E9	1299
F	Total number of contacts to policymakers and public bodies with communication materials (as each recipient of communication materials may receive several consignments during the project, each time a recipient receives them is counted here.)	E1, E2, E9	4481
G	Percentage of identified policymakers and public bodies (A) participating in activities of the project, including workshops as speakers or participants.	E3, E4, E5, E6, E8	51.4%
H	Simplified qualitative external evaluation of the communication with policymakers and public bodies plan by a sample of members of the IAB and of supporting organisations, where each of the following qualitative parameters will be assessed (ranked from 1, very poor to 10 excellent):		
	Adequacy of the list of policymakers and public bodies.	E5, E7	9
	Adequacy of the objectives of the communication strategy with policymakers and public bodies.		10
	Adequacy of communication materials used.		9
	Adequacy of the actions carried out.		10
	Degree of implementation of the communication plan with policymakers and public bodies.		8
	Overall quality of the communication plan with policymakers and public bodies.		9
Overall impact of the communication plan with policymakers and public bodies	8		

6 Conclusions

This deliverable displays and evaluates the activities carried out over these 36 months to reach policymakers and public bodies.

Communication requirements were set in *D7.6* while the plan was in *D7.7*. All Consortium Members must use both documents together to ensure the correct execution of the plan and the fulfilment of the objectives.

D7.9 Evaluation report for communications with policymakers (2|2) will complete the evaluation of these activities in project month 48.

7 References

The following references have been used for the preparation of this deliverable:

- DIGIECOQUARRY Grant Agreement number 101003750.

WP7

- D7.6 Requirements for communication with policymakers and public bodies.
- D7.7 Communications with Policymakers Plan.

WP9

- D9.1 Dissemination, communication, and exploitation plan.
- D9.2 DIGIECOQUARRY's website.
- D9.3, D9.5, D9.8 Dissemination and communication materials.
- D9.4, D9.6, D9.9 Report on communication and dissemination activities

List of Figures

Figure 1 Type of action – Number.....	10
Figure 2 Type of action - %.....	11
Figure 3. DEQ workshop's opening, Spain.....	12
Figure 4. DEQ at PDAC 2023 fair, Canada.	12
Figure 5. DEQ at Hannover Messe fair, Germany.....	12
Figure 6. DEQ at ANEFA's General Assembly 2023, Spain.....	12
Figure 7. DEQ at GAIN Summit, Korea.....	12
Figure 8. DEQ at Mining and Energy International Congress, Spain.....	12
Figure 9 Information conveyed through- Number of times.....	13
Figure 10 Dissemination channel used - %.	13
Figure 11 Actions with incidence into policy makers (by category).	14
Figure 12 Percentage of actions reaching types of policymakers (by category).....	15
Figure 13 Types of policymakers - %.	15
Figure 14 Neutral Aggregates cover.	16

List of Tables

Table 1 KPI table.	18
-------------------------	----

Annex 1. Actions

Type of action	Partner leading the action	Name of the action	Date	Place	Country	Type of meeting	Action	Invited/Receptors	Attendant/Participants
Meeting	ANEFA	AFAPA Delegates Assembly	2021/06/04	Oviedo	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	60	52
Meeting	ANEFA	AFA Balears Delegates Assembly	2021/06/07	Palma de Mallorca	Spain	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	24	18
Meeting	ANEFA	COMINROC Executive Committee	2021/06/08	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Verbal information	16	12
Meeting	ANEFA	AFA Andalucía Delegates Assembly	2021/06/11	Antequera	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	80	63
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG General Assembly 2021	2021/06/18	Brussels	Belgium	Videoconference	Verbal information	90	77
Meeting	ANEFA	AFA Castilla La Mancha	2021/06/21	Toledo	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	45	32
Meeting	ANEFA	AFA La Rioja	2021/06/22	Logroño	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	30	21
Meeting	ANEFA	AFARIME Navarra	2021/06/23	Pamplona	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	35	29
Meeting	ANEFA	ANEFA Board meeting	2021/07/01	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	28	16
Meeting	ANEFA	FdA Board meeting	2021/07/02	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	22	20
Meeting	ANEFA	VI Aggregates National Congress - Committee Meetings	2021/07/14	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	90	73
Meeting	ANEFA	La Granda Course on Raw Materials	2021/08/04	Avilés	Spain	Face to face	Verbal information	unknown	60
Meeting	ANEFA	COMINROC Executive Committee	2021/09/08	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Verbal information	16	15
Meeting	ANEFA	ANEFA Board meeting	2021/09/16	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	28	18
Meeting	ANEFA	FdA Board meeting	2021/09/17	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	22	16
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG Climate Change TF	2021/09/20	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	10	9
Meeting	ANEFA	CEPCO Board meeting	2021/09/23	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Verbal information	21	15
Interview	ANEFA	Aggregates Business Europe	2021/10/04	Madrid	Spain	Videoconference	Verbal information	1	1

Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG - Environment Committee	2021/10/14	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	40	26
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG - H&S Committee	2021/10/14	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	35	27
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG - Technical Committee	2021/10/15	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	21	17
Meeting	ANEFA	ANIET Technical meeting	2021/11/11	Porto	Portugal	Face to face	Part of a presentation	unknown	250
Meeting	ANEFA	DEQ International Advisory Board	2021/11/16	Madrid	Spain	Videoconference	Complete specific presentation	10	8
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG Board Meeting	2021/11/19	Bratislava	Slovakia	Hybrid	Verbal information	25	19
Meeting	ANEFA	Sumex Project Workshop	2021/11/23	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Verbal information	unknown	40
Workshop	ANEFA	Technical Workshop "Channelling knowledge from European projects into the Raw Materials Information System (RMIS)	2021/12/03	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Liaison meeting	unknown	unknown
Meeting	ANEFA	GAIN meeting	2021/12/09	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Verbal information	50	24
Meeting	ANEFA	ANEFA Board meeting	2021/12/15	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	28	15
Meeting	ANEFA	FdA Board meeting	2021/12/16	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	22	18
Meeting	ANEFA	COMINROC Executive Committee	2021/12/21	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Verbal information	16	11
Meeting	ANEFA	Advisory Board ETSI Mines and Energy	2022/01/19	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Verbal information	20	15
Meeting	ANEFA	PRIMIGEA Executive Committee	2022/02/01	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	10	7
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG - Water Management TF	2022/02/08	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	12	6
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG Climate Change TF	2022/02/09	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	15	15
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG - RDS & EPD WG	2022/02/10	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	13	8
Meeting	ANEFA	COMINROC Executive Committee	2022/02/11	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Verbal information	16	13
Meeting	ANEFA	ANEFA Board meeting	2022/02/16	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	28	22
Meeting	ANEFA	FdA Board meeting	2022/02/17	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	22	19

Meeting	ANEFA	CEPCO Board meeting	2022/03/03	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Verbal information	21	13
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG - Technical Committee	2022/03/15	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	21	20
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG - Environment Committee	2022/03/17	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	39	23
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG - H&S Committee	2022/03/17	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	35	27
Meeting	ANEFA	Sumex Project Pilot Week	2022/03/21-24	Tarragona	Spain	Hybrid	Liaison meeting	30	30
Meeting	ANEFA	COMINROC Executive Committee	2022/04/01	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Verbal information	16	9
Workshop	ANEFA	EIT Raw Materials Workshop	2022/04/05	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Roundtable	unknown	unknown
Meeting	ANEFA	PRIMIGEA Executive Committee	2022/04/08	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	10	
Meeting	ANEFA	President of the regional Government of Asturias	2022/04/11	Oviedo	Spain	Face to face	Verbal information	3	3
Meeting	ANEFA	FdA Board meeting	2022/04/19	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	22	19
Meeting	ANEFA	ANEFA Board meeting	2022/04/20	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	28	20
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG Board Meeting	2022/04/28	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Verbal information	25	20
Meeting	ANEFA	AFA Madrid	2022/05/11	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	20	18
Meeting	ANEFA	CEPCO Board meeting	2022/05/17	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Verbal information	22	16
Meeting	ANEFA	Mining Safety Permanent Commission	2022/05/19	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Verbal information	16	16
Workshop	ANEFA	VI Aggregates National Congress	2022/05/25	Oviedo	Spain	Face to face	Workshop	5000	810
Meeting	ANEFA	UGT Trade Union	2022/06/07	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	4	4
Workshop	ANEFA	UEPG Entrepreneur Forum	2022/06/16	Larnaka	Cyprus	Face to face	Workshop	150	85
Workshop	ANEFA	Sumex Workshop	2022/06/22	Sevilla	Spain	Face to face	Liaison meeting	80	63
Meeting	ANEFA	Mining Safety Commission	2022/06/23	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Verbal information	36	32
Meeting	ANEFA	AFA Andalucía Delegates Assembly	2022/06/24	Antequera	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	80	63

Meeting	ANEFA	AFAPA Delegates Assembly	2022/06/30	Oviedo	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	60	52
Meeting	ANEFA	AFARCYL Delegates Assembly	2022/07/01	Valladolid	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	80	63
Meeting	ANEFA	GAIN meeting	2022/07/06	Madrid	Spain	Videoconference	Verbal information	42	23
Meeting	ANEFA	FdA Board meeting	2022/07/08	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	22	14
Meeting	ANEFA	COMINROC Executive Committee	2022/09/02	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Verbal information	16	12
Meeting	ANEFA	R8 Kick off meeting	2022/09/05-06	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Verbal information	150	65
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG PR & Communication TF	2022/09/07	Brussels	Belgium	Videoconference	Verbal information	15	7
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG Biodiversity TF	2022/09/08	Brussels	Belgium	Videoconference	Verbal information	20	12
Meeting	ANEFA	Subdirección General de Minas	2022/09/13	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Complete specific presentation	2	2
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG Recycling TF	2022/09/16	Brussels	Belgium	Videoconference	Part of a presentation	25	22
Meeting	ANEFA	Fundación Minería y Vida	2022/09/27	Madrid	Spain	Videoconference	Verbal information	25	23
Meeting	ANEFA	ANEFA Board meeting	2022/09/28	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Complete specific presentation	28	17
Meeting	ANEFA	ANEFA - ANEFHOP (DG)	2022/10/14	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Complete specific presentation	2	2
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG - Environment Committee	2022/10/17	Alicante	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	38	26
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG - H&S Committee	2022/10/17	Alicante	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	35	24
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG - Technical Committee	2022/10/18	Alicante	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	21	19
Meeting	ANEFA	COMINROC Executive Committee	2022/10/19	Seville	Spain	Hybrid	Verbal information	16	14
Meeting	ANEFA	FdA Board meeting	2022/10/20	Seville	Spain	Hybrid	Complete specific presentation	22	16
Meeting	ANEFA	PRIMIGEIA Executive Committee	2022/10/20	Seville	Spain	Hybrid	Verbal information	10	10
Meeting	ANEFA	Euskal Árido Delegates Assembly	2022/10/27	Bilbao	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	90	65

Meeting	ANEFA, Asogravass	GAIN meeting in Korea	2022/11/14-17	Seoul	Korea	Face to face	Part of a presentation	200	150
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG Sustainable Development Awards	2022/11/30	Brussels	Belgium	Face to face	Verbal information	400	250
Meeting	ANEFA	COMINROC Executive Committee	2022/12/02	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Verbal information	16	11
Meeting	ANEFA	ANEFA Board meeting	2022/12/14	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Note in the report, Verbal information	28	22
Meeting	ANEFA	FdA Board meeting	2022/12/15	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Note in the report, Verbal information	22	15
Meeting	ANEFA	AFAPA Delegates Assembly	2022/12/16	Oviedo	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	60	48
Meeting	ANEFA	Fundación Minería y Vida	2022/12/21	Madrid	Spain	Videoconferenc e	Verbal information	25	21
Meeting	ANEFA	Economic management of aggregates sites meeting	2023//24-25	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	200	82
Meeting	ANEFA	CEPCO Board meeting	2023/01/18	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Verbal information	22	13
Meeting	ANEFA	MITERD - Expert Group Roadmap Action Plan	2023/02/01	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	45	42
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG PR & Communication TF	2023/02/08	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Verbal information	15	9
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG Water TF	2023/02/08	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	13	12
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG Biodiversity TF	2023/02/09	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	20	14
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG Climate Change TF	2023/02/10	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	16	16
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG RDS&EPD WG	2023/02/10	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	20	9
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG Recycling TF	2023/02/17	Larnaka	Cyprus	Face to face	Part of a presentation	25	19
Meeting	ANEFA	FdA Board meeting	2023/02/22	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Note in the report, Verbal information	22	20
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG Working Group on Biodiversity Indicators	2023/02/22	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Liaison meeting	15	11
Meeting	ANEFA	ANEFA Board meeting	2023/02/23	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Note in the report, Verbal information	28	23

Meeting	ANEFA	COMINROC Executive Committee	2023/02/24	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Verbal information	16	15
Fair & Congress	ANEFA	PDAC 2023	2023/03/05-08	Toronto	Canada	Face to face	Verbal information, Stand	unknown	50
Meeting	ANEFA	PRIMIGEA Executive Committee	2023/03/10	Madrid	Spain	Videoconference	Verbal information	10	9
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG - Environment Committee	2023/03/16	Lisbon	Portugal	Face to face	Part of a presentation	39	23
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG - H&S Committee	2023/03/16	Lisbon	Portugal	Face to face	Part of a presentation	35	27
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG - Technical Committee	2023/03/17	Lisbon	Portugal	Face to face	Part of a presentation	21	20
Meeting	ANEFA	Asturias Regional Expert Group on Raw Materials	2023/03/24	Oviedo	Spain	Hybrid	Verbal information	25	16
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG Working Group on Biodiversity Indicators	2023/03/31	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Liaison meeting	18	14
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG Air Quality TF	2023/04/03	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Verbal information	17	13
Meeting	ANEFA	UNE TC 146 Aggregates Plenary meeting	2023/04/11	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	90	37
Meeting	ANEFA	ANEFA Board meeting	2023/04/12	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Note in the report, Verbal information	28	15
Meeting	ANEFA	Spanish Geological Survey	2023/04/13	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	4	4
Fair & Congress	ANEFA	Hannover Messe	2023/04/18-19	Hannover	Germany	Face to face	Complete specific presentation	30	15
Meeting	ANEFA	Euskal Árido Delegates Assembly	2023/04/20	San Sebastián	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	90	72
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG Board Meeting	2023/04/26	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Note in the report, Verbal information	25	22
Meeting	ANEFA	ARIGAL Delegates Assembly	2023/04/28	Santiago de Compostela	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	150	117
Meeting	ANEFA	Energy efficiency management of aggregates sites meeting	2023/05/03	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	150	63
Meeting	ANEFA	ANEFA Delegates Assembly	2023/05/04	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Part of a presentation, Roll Up	450	190
Meeting	ANEFA	AFARCYL Delegates Assembly	2023/05/11	Valladolid	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	70	37

Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG Climate Change TF	2023/05/17	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	17	14
Meeting	ANEFA	Junta de Andalucía Meeting	2023/05/18	Seville	Spain	Face to face	Complete specific presentation	2	2
Meeting	ANEFA	PRIMIGEA Executive Committee	2023/05/18	Madrid	Spain	Videoconference	Part of a presentation	10	10
Meeting	ANEFA	FdA Delegates Assembly	2023/05/24	Barcelona	Spain	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	22	18
Meeting	ANEFA	CEPCO Delegates Assembly	2023/05/30	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Verbal information	42	28
Meeting	ANEFA	AFAPA Delegates Assembly	2023/06/07	Oviedo	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	60	45
Meeting	ANEFA	CSIC IGME	2023/06/09	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Complete specific presentation	6	6
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG Delegates Assembly	2023/06/16	Stockholm	Sweden	Face to face	Complete specific presentation , Neutral aggregates	80	74
Meeting	ANEFA	Spanish Mining Safety Committee	2023/06/20	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Verbal information	45	40
Meeting	ANEFA	Spanish Secretary of State of Energy	2023/06/20	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Verbal information	2	2
Meeting	ANEFA	ANEFA Board meeting	2023/06/21	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Note in the report, Verbal information	28	19
Meeting	ANEFA	Global Aggregates Information Network	2023/07/03-04	Queenstown	New Zealand	Face to face	Complete specific presentation , Neutral aggregates	60	52
Meeting	ANEFA	CCOO	2023/08/07	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Complete specific presentation	3	3
Fair & Congress	Asogras	5° Internacional Concrete Sustainability Conference	2023/08/28-29	Bogotá	Colombia	Face to face	Complete specific presentation	40	300
Meeting	ANEFA	UGT	2023/09/07	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	4	4
Meeting	ANEFA	ANEFA Board meeting	2023/09/13	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Note in the report, Verbal information	28	21
Meeting	ANEFA	FdA Board meeting	2023/09/14	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Note in the report, Verbal information	22	19

Meeting	ANEFA	Euroschottertagung	2023/09/15	Würzburg am Main	Germany	Hybrid	Complete specific presentation , Neutral aggregates	75	48
Meeting	ANEFA	Spanish Minister of Ecological Transition & Demographic Challenge	2023/09/18	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Verbal information	4	4
Meeting	ANEFA	ARIVAL Delegates Assembly	2023/09/22	Castellón	Spain	Face to face	Complete specific presentation	140	85
Meeting	ANEFA	Visit to Canteras Industriales site - DG Minas of Andalucía	2023/09/26	Granada	Spain	Face to face	Complete specific presentation	55	53
Fair & Congress	Asogras	IV Seminario Internacional de Minería y Planeamiento Minero	2023/09/7-8	Medellín	Colombia	Face to face	Verbal information, Stand	50	300
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG Recycling TF	2023/10/02	Vienna	Austria	Face to face	Part of a presentation	25	18
Meeting	ANEFA	ANDECE Decarbonisation Technical Conference	2023/10/05	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Complete specific presentation	30	27
Meeting	ANEFA	Director General of Mines of Murcia Region	2023/10/09	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Note in the report, Verbal information	2	2
Meeting	ANEFA	AFA Andalucía Board meeting	2023/10/10	Arcos de la Frontera	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	18	15
Webinar	ANEFA	EPD Webinar	2023/10/11	Madrid	Spain	Videoconference	Part of a presentation	250	92
Fair & Congress	Chalmers University	SBMI Branch Day	2023/10/12	Gothenburg	Sweden	Face to face	Part of a presentation	200	180
Meeting	ANEFA	COMINROC Delegates Assembly	2023/10/16	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	20	15
Webinar	ANEFA	Climate Neutrality Webinar	2023/10/17	Madrid	Spain	Videoconference	Part of a presentation	200	67
Meeting	ANEFA	Director General of Industry - MINCOTUR	2023/10/17	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Verbal information	2	2
Meeting	ANEFA	CEN TC 154 Aggregates Plenary meeting	2023/10/19	Vienna	Austria	Face to face	Verbal information	50	28
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG - Environment Committee	2023/10/19	Brussels	Belgium	Face to face	Part of a presentation	39	27
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG - H&S Committee	2023/10/19	Brussels	Belgium	Face to face	Part of a presentation	35	22
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG - Technical Committee	2023/10/19	Brussels	Belgium	Face to face	Part of a presentation	21	17

Meeting	ANEFA	Journée de l'Industrie Chaufournière Belge	2023/10/27	Charleroi	Belgium	Face to face	Complete specific presentation , Neutral aggregates	200	160
Meeting	ANEFA	CSIC IGME	2023/11/02	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Verbal information	7	7
Meeting	ANEFA	ANIET Technical meeting	2023/11/08	Porto	Portugal	Face to face	Part of a presentation	200	180
Meeting	ANEFA	FdA Board meeting	2023/11/09	Porto	Portugal	Hybrid	Note in the report, Verbal information	22	14
Fair & Congress	Chalmers University	Critical Raw Materials Week	2023/11/13 -17	Brussels	Belgium	Face to face	Verbal information		30
Meeting	ANEFA	AFAPA Delegates Assembly	2023/11/17	Oviedo	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	60	52
Fair & Congress	ANEFA	International Congress on Energy and Mineral Resources	2023/11/22 -23	León	Spain	Face to face	Complete specific presentation , Stand	400	380
Fair & Congress	ANEFA	SMOPYC - International Exhibition of Machinery for Public Works, Construction and Mining	2023/11/22 -23	Zaragoza	Spain	Face to face	Verbal information, Stand	250	90
Meeting	ANEFA	ANEFA Board meeting	2023/11/23	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Note in the report, Verbal information	28	17
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG Board Meeting	2023/11/30	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Verbal information	25	20
Meeting	UPM-AI	Raw Materials Week Workshop	2023/11/16	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Part of a presentation , Roll Up	100	100
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG Board Meeting	2023/12/01	Brussels	Belgium	Hybrid	Verbal information	25	24
Meeting	ANEFA	COMINROC Executive Committee	2023/12/11	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Verbal information	16	14
Meeting	ANEFA	CEPCO Board meeting	2023/12/15	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Verbal information	23	14
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG Presidential Strategy Meeting	2024/01/12	Brussels	Belgium	Face to face	Verbal information	48	32
Meeting	ANEFA	UNE General Director Meeting	2024/01/18	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Complete specific presentation	3	3
Training Course	ANEFA	MINING & RAW MATERIALS MBA	2024/01/19	Seville	Spain	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	12	10

Meeting	ANEFA	ANEFA - ANEFHOP (DG)	2024/02/02	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Complete specific presentation	1	1
Meeting	ANEFA	AFA Balears Delegates Assembly	2024/02/21	Palma de Mallorca	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	24	22
Meeting	ANEFA	PRIMIGEA Executive Committee	2024/02/23	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Verbal information	32	19
Meeting	ANEFA	ANEFA Board meeting	2024/02/29	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Note in the report, Verbal information	28	17
Workshop	ANEFA, Chalmers, UPM-AI	European Seminar on aggregates digitalisation	2024/03-05	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Complete specific presentation	200	200
Meeting	ANEFA	FdA Board meeting	2024/03/01	Porto	Portugal	Hybrid	Note in the report, Verbal information	22	14
Fair & Congress	ANEFA	PDAC 2024	2024/03/02-06	Totonto	Canada	Face to face	Verbal information, Stand	unknown	50
Workshop	ANEFA	DEQ Workshop	2024/03/04	Oviedo	Spain	Face to face	Complete specific presentation	200	35
Workshop	ANEFA	Mining Technical Workshop	2024/03/06	Torrelavega	Spain	Face to face	Complete specific presentation	30	28
Meeting	ANEFA	ASGB Association Suisse de l'industrie des Graviers et du Béton	2024/03/15	Montreaux	Switzerland	Face to face	Complete specific presentation, Neutral aggregates	150	75
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG - Environment Committee	2024/03/19	Bucharest	Romania	Face to face	Part of a presentation	39	27
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG - H&S Committee	2024/03/19	Bucharest	Romania	Face to face	Part of a presentation	35	22
Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG - Technical Committee	2024/03/20	Bucharest	Romania	Face to face	Part of a presentation	21	17
Meeting	ANEFA	Murcia Region Environment Minister	2024/03/25	Murcia	Spain	Face to face	Verbal information	4	4
Training Course	ANEFA	MINING & RAW MATERIALS MBA	2024/04/05	Seville	Spain	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	12	10
Meeting	ANEFA	DEQ International Advisory Board	2024/04/11	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Complete specific presentation	10	7
Meeting	ANEFA	PRIMIGEA Executive Committee	2024/04/12	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Verbal information	32	22
Fair & Congress	UPM-AI	The challenges in Mineral Raw Materials: Training and Research	2024/04/23	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Verbal information	50	50

Meeting	ANEFA	UEPG Board Meeting	2024/04/25	Brussels	Belgium	Face to face	Verbal information	25	21
Fair & Congress	Asograva s	Forum of Latin American and Caribbean Countries on Sustainable Development 2024	2024/04/8-10	Chile	Santiago de Chile	Face to face	Verbal information	50	500
Meeting	ANEFA	ANEFA Delegates Assembly	2024/05/09	Madrid	Spain	Face to face	Part of a presentation	450	205
Meeting	ANEFA	FdA Delegates Assembly	2024/05/10	Madrid	Spain	Hybrid	Part of a presentation	22	15
Fair & Congress	ANEFA	Raw Materials Summit	2024/05/14-16	Brussels	Belgium	Face to face	Liaison meeting	unknown	unknown

Annex 2. Policymakers list

Surname		Country	Type of policymaker
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Hwang	China	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Barco	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Barroso	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Caballero	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Columba	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Faundez	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Villanueva	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Contreras	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Gómez	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Madrigal	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Carrasco	Spain	ICT & suppliers industries
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rodríguez	Spain	ICT & suppliers industries
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rojas	Spain	ICT & suppliers industries
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Salgado	Spain	ICT & suppliers industries
Mr/Ms/Mrs	González	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ramírez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Alonso	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Martín	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Perez	Spain	ICT & suppliers industries
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Vázquez	Spain	ICT & suppliers industries
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Woodford	United Kingdom	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Fincke	Europe	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Langford	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Sarasa	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ariza	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Bieberach	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	González	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations

Mr/Ms/Mrs	González	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	López	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Tejela	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rodríguez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Cabal	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Cerati	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rivero	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Aladro	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rebordinos	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Aguado	Spain	Construction sector and other clients. Others
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Fernández	Spain	Construction sector and other clients. Others
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Carrera	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Peraita	Spain	Construction sector and other clients. Others
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Castagna	Italy	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Jarauta	Spain	Construction sector and other clients. Others
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pinto	Portugal	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Morrey	Canada	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Tasende	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Torrents	Spain	Certification bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Scott	New Zealand	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Moreno	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Soneyro	Argentina	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pauner	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	García	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Badiola	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pérez	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	García	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Valens	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Cortés	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Lago	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations

Mr/Ms/Mrs	Novoa	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Puente	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Barella	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Bernat	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Guerrero	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Marmaneu	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Monfort	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Serrano	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Fuertes	Spain	Citizens and civil society
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Castellano	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Tirado	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ceballos	Spain	Environmental NGOs
Mr/Ms/Mrs	De la Villa	Spain	Environmental NGOs
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Caballos	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Lavandeira	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Fernández	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pedraza	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Arranz	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	di Luca	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	González	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Massó	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pedreño	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Prieto	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ramírez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Sumillera	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Alonso	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Gaona	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Gutiérrez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ramírez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Arbaizar	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations

Mr/Ms/Mrs	Gómez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Durán	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Bellón	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ropero	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Janssen	Germany	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Nelles	Germany	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Thilo	Germany	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs		Korea	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Fernández	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Sánchez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	García - Lostal	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ruiz	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Binimelis	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Cuadrado	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Bruno	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Bernat	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	van der Plas	Netherlands	Certification bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	van der Voort	Netherlands	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Montoya	Spain	Citizens and civil society
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Acevedo	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Sánchez	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Silva	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Barragán	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Crespo	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	de la Hija	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Alaejos	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pedrajas	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Moreno	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pando	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Domenech	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations

Mr/Ms/Mrs	Toribio	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Menéndez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Terán	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Busqué	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ferrandis	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Herranz	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Masa	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Orell	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rodríguez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rivero	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	García	Spain	Construction sector and other clients. Construction Products Confederations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	García	Spain	Construction sector and other clients. Construction Products Confederations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rodulfo	Spain	Construction sector and other clients. Construction Products Confederations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Moya	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rohrer	Spain	Environmental NGOs
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Menéndez	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Abad	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Alfonso	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Beltrá	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Fernández	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Hita	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Llinares	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Lozano	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Cañal	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Alfonso	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Alonso	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Bernardo	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Elorza	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Javier	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Manuel	Spain	Academia and researchers

Mr/Ms/Mrs	María	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Mata	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Parcerisa	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Parra	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rodríguez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	López	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Prado	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Fernández	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Loeck	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Mendiola	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Valle	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Picanyol	Spain	Citizens and civil society
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ceballos	Spain	Environmental NGOs
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Fedaoui	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ruiz	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Coullaut	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Regueiro	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Latouros	Cyprus	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Amado	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Carusan	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Manrique	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Gutiérrez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Barata	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	García	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Faria	Portugal	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pelegry	Spain	ICT & suppliers industries
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Aneas	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Jurado	Europe	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Schäfer	Europe	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Mailing	Spain	Communication media

Mr/Ms/Mrs	Mailing	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ojea	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rego	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Díaz	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Mailing	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Mailing	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	González	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Porter	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pérez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Suffys	Europe	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Muñoz	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Quiros	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ángel	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Gallego	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Lieck	Europe	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Omedas	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Kuby	Europe	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Cavaco-Viegas	Europe	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Herrera	Europe	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pellegrini	Europe	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Fornea	Romania	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Montalvo	Europe	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Cibrian	Europe	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Sabbatelli	Europe	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Hollis	Europe	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Oliveira	Europe	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Echave	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ezquerria	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Portugués	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Santa	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations

Mr/Ms/Mrs	Mailing	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ortolan	France	Certification bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Andrada	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Argaiz	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Fernández	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Gordo	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Gozalo	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Puig	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Roca	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ruberte	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Sánchez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Sánchez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Tornero	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Calozet	Belgium	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Petit	Belgium	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Leon	Spain	ICT & suppliers industries
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Bouso	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	María	Spain	ICT & suppliers industries
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Fueyo	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	García	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Haddad	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	García	Spain	Public interest Foundations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rosado	Spain	Public interest Foundations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Luis	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Isidro	Spain	Environmental NGOs
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pérez	Spain	Environmental NGOs
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Gradischnig	Austria	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Steiner	Austria	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Moreno	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Otxoa	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations

Mr/Ms/Mrs	Murlidhar	India	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	O'Brien	Ireland	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Álvarez	Spain	Citizens and civil society
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Domínguez	Spain	Citizens and civil society
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Jeréz	Spain	Citizens and civil society
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Leandro	Spain	Citizens and civil society
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Querol	Spain	Citizens and civil society
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Olloqui	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Salazar	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pietro	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Blanco	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Leiva	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Masó	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Navarro	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Porro	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Puig	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rodríguez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Prado	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rui	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ferrer	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Flores	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Herrerias	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Velar	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Berenguer	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Molina	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Mora	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Córdoba	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Traba	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Navarro	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Osorio	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations

Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pereira	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Jewell	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Fernández	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Cruz	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Cámara	Spain	Citizens and civil society
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Cámara	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ignacio	Spain	Citizens and civil society
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Vázquez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Cañas	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	López	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rognoni	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Santiago	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Cezón	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	García	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	García	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Gegúndez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	López	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Cervera	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Monge	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pérez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Santiago	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pérez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rodríguez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Feixas	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Bailly-Bailliere	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Fernández	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Bartolome	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Martínez	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Jordá	Spain	Citizens and civil society
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Martín	Spain	Citizens and civil society

Mr/Ms/Mrs	Núñez	Spain	Citizens and civil society
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pieren	Spain	Citizens and civil society
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Regueiro	Spain	Citizens and civil society
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Lefebvre	Europe	Citizens and civil society
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Muriel	Spain	Certification bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Sevillano	Spain	Certification bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rodríguez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	de Aspe	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Martín	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pérez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Lara	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	López	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Muñoz	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Cabezas	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Hermoso	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Garbarino	Europe	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Orveillon	Europe	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Saveyn	Europe	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Barthe	Europe	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Eder	Europe	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Lamperti	Europe	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Luque	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	López	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rodríguez	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Vázquez	Spain	Certification bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Baños	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Margareto	Spain	ICT & suppliers industries
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Creixell	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Mora	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Jiménez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations

Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rodríguez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Baños	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Josa	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pilar	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ribeiro	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pilato	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Casado	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Bermejo	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Carrillo	Spain	ICT & suppliers industries
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pascual	Spain	ICT & suppliers industries
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Fernandes	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Bilbao	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	CAÑAS	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	del Castillo	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Gálvez	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	González	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	González	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	LUENA	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Montserrat	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rodríguez	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rodríguez-Piñero	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Artigas	Spain	ICT & suppliers industries
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Santos	Spain	ICT & suppliers industries
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Puche	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Hormaeche	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ortega	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	López	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	BARRENECHEA	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Gordo	Spain	Citizens and civil society
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Vilaplana	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations

Mr/Ms/Mrs	Bone	United Kingdom	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	James	United Kingdom	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Prichard	United Kingdom	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Wharton	Europe	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Kheng	Malaysia	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Colilla	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Effraïmidou	Europe	Citizens and civil society
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Lumen	Europe	Citizens and civil society
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Heutinck	Netherlands	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Morales	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Holmen	Norway	Certification bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Stanley	USA	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Bartolomé	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Cascajero	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Cuadrado	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Haro	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Martín	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Romay	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Vallina	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Zaragoza	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	ROS	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Mouttaqi	Morocco	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Menéndez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Canteli	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Gómez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Álvarez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	de Ceballos	Spain	Environmental NGOs
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Marín	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Gutiérrez	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Targhetta	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations

Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rodrigues	Germany	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Colomina	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Torrescasana	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ventura	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Burkhalter	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ignacio	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Tertre	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Portillo	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Sánchez	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Breto	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	López	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Vallés	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Cofiño	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Berjano	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Díaz	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Martín	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pola	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Roqueñí	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Alvear	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Arasti	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Causí	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ceballos	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Gil	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Media	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	García	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Gómez	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Guirao	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Haro	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Jara	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	López	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies

Mr/Ms/Mrs	Arranz	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Arroyo	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rodríguez	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Carbonell	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Mas	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ruiz	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Coutinho	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Uría	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Uría	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Dorado	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Esteban	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Infante	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Manzanos	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Osés	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rubio	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Urquía	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Aparicio	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Paños	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Sánchez	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Aierdi	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Gómez	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Goñi	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Irujo	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Itoiz	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Itoiz	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Muñoz	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Mir	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Morro	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pons	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Urkiaga	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies

Mr/Ms/Mrs	Artiles	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Batista	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Castilla	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Fernández	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Franquis	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Luaces	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Navarro	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Valbuena	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Alonso	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Cerdá	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Martínez	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Martínez	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Piquer	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Puig	Spain	Citizens and civil society
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Puig	Spain	Citizens and civil society
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Chimenos	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	García	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ruiz	Spain	ICT & suppliers industries
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Almefelt	Sweden	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Sohlman	Sweden	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Tengsved	Sweden	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	López	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Mazadiego	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Parra	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	González	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Abrantes	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Saldaña	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Abella	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Carballo	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Freijo	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies

Mr/Ms/Mrs	Menéndez	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Cámara	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Gómez	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Guarner	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	López	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rodríguez	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ruiz	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Torrejón	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Ulargui	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Flores	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Cobo	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	González	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	García	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Rubio	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Lobo	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Moreno	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Madrigal	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Carnero	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Oría	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	de Juan	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Solano	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Fernández	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Pérez	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Aragón	Spain	Certification bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Moya	Spain	Certification bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Alarcón	Spain	Certification bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	García	Spain	Certification bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Vidal	Spain	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Chuah	Switzerland	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Peduzzi	Worldwide	Official policymakers and funding bodies

Mr/Ms/Mrs	VANDER	Switzerland	Official policymakers and funding bodies
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Bodet	France	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Calero	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Quintana	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Amez	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Vega	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Mahy	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Aguirre-Jofré	Spain	Academia and researchers
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Colson	France	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Fernández	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Veintimilla	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Aguilera	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	García	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	González	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Cerezo	Spain	Citizens and civil society
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Artieda	Spain	Entrepreneur organisations. M&Q Associations
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Arce	Spain	Communication media
Mr/Ms/Mrs	Fajardo	Spain	Citizens and civil society